

PUBLIC HEALTH INSTITUTE NIŠ
ИНСТИТУТ ЗА ЈАВНО ЗДРАВЉЕ НИШ

FACULTY OF MEDICINE NIŠ
МЕДИЦИНСКИ ФАКУЛТЕТ НИШ

SERBIAN MEDICAL SOCIETY OF NIŠ
СРПСКО ЛЕКАРСКО ДРУШТВО ПОДРУЖНИЦА НИШ

52nd DAYS OF PREVENTIVE MEDICINE
52. ДАНИ ПРЕВЕНТИВНЕ МЕДИЦИНЕ

INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS
МЕЂУНАРОДНИ КОНГРЕС

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS
ЗБОРНИК РЕЗИМЕА

НИШ, 2018.

Editor in Chief

Уредник
Prof. dr Biljana Kocić

Technical Editor

Технички уредник
dipl. ing. Stefan Bogdanović

Publisher

Издавач
Public Health Institute Niš – Институт за јавно здравље Ниш
Faculty of Medicine Niš, University of Niš – Медицински факултет у Нишу, Универзитет у Нишу
Serbian Medical Society of Niš – Српско лекарско друштво подружница Ниш

For publisher

За издавача
Prof. dr Miodrag Stojanović

Printed in

Штампарија и место штампања
Галаксија, Ниш, Србија

Number of copies

Тираж
350

Under the patronage of

Под покровитељством

Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia

Министарства просвете, науке и технолошког развоја Републике Србије

Ministry of Health of the Republic of Serbia

Министарства здравља Републике Србије

All abstracts are published in the book of abstracts in the form in which they were submitted by the authors, who are responsible for their content.
Сви сажеци су публиковани у зборнику резимеа у облику у коме су достављени од стране аутора, који су одговорни за њихов садржај.

The content of this publication is available online at dpm.izjz-nis.org.rs
Садржај ове публикације је доступан на Интернет адреси dpm.izjz-nis.org.rs

Dr Stanko Marjanović is participating in realisation of the Museum of Health Culture exposition.

У реализацији изложбе у Музеју здравствене културе учествује др Станко Марјановић.

The continuing education program number A-1-1253/18 was accredited by the decision of the Health Council of the Republic of Serbia No. 153-02-1550/2018-01 from 21. 05. 2018.

Програм континуиране едукације је под бројем А-1-1253/18 акредитован одлуком Здравственог савета Републике Србије број: 153-02-1550/2018-01 од 21. 05. 2018. године.

ISBN 978-86-915991-9-5

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE – НАУЧНИ ОДБОР

Chairlady/Председница

Prof. dr Biljana Kocić, Serbia

Members/Чланови

Prof. dr Dobrila Stanković-Đorđević, Serbia

Prof. dr Miodrag Stojanović, Serbia

Prof. dr Dragan Bogdanović, Serbia

Prof. dr Eleni Jelastopulu, Greece

Prof. dr Gianfranco Damiani, Italy

Prof. dr Angel Galabov, Bulgaria

Prof. dr Tomaz Langerholc, Slovenia

Prof. dr Gordana Mijović, Montenegro

Prof. dr Olgica Đurković-Đaković, Serbia

Prof. dr Lazar Ranin, Serbia

Prof. dr Milena Kataranovski, Serbia

Prof. dr Branislava Kocić, Serbia

Prof. dr Suzana Otašević, Serbia

Prof. dr Marina Dinić, Serbia

Prof. dr Biljana Miljković-Selimović, Serbia

Prof. dr Gordana Ranđelović, Serbia

Prof. dr Nataša Miladinović-Tasić, Serbia

Doc. dr Predrag Stojanović, Serbia

Prof. dr Zoran Milošević, Serbia

Prof. dr Vesna Mijatović-Jovanović, Serbia

Doc. dr Aleksandar Višnjić, Serbia

Prof. dr Maja Nikolić, Serbia

Prof. dr Dušica Stojanović, Serbia

Prof. dr Aleksandra Stanković, Serbia

Doc. dr Konstansa Lazarević, Serbia

Doc. dr Olivera Radulović, Serbia

Doc. dr Nataša Rančić, Serbia

Doc. dr Roberta Marković, Serbia

Doc. dr Ljiljana Stošić, Serbia

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији - Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

614.4(048)

616-084(048)

INTERNATIONAL Congress Days of Preventive Medicine (52; 2018; Niš)
Book of Abstracts - Зборник резимеа / 52nd Days of Preventive Medicine, International Congress [25-28. September 2018. Niš] - 52. Дани превентивне медицине, међународни конгрес; [endorsed by] Public Health Institute Niš [and] Faculty of Medicine Niš [and] Serbian Medical Society of Niš - [у организацији] Институт за јавно здравље Ниш [и] Медицински факултет Ниш [и] Српско лекарско друштво подружница Ниш; [editor in chief, уредник Biljana Kosić]. – Niš : Public Health Institute : Faculty of Medicine : Serbian Medical Society, 2018 (Ниш : Галаксија). - 240 str. : ilustr. ; 30 cm

Tiraž 350. - Bibliografija uz pojedine apstrakte.

ISBN 978-86-915991-9-5 (PHI)

1. Public Health Institute (Niš) 2. Faculty of Medicine (Niš) 3. Serbian Medical Society (Niš)

а) Превентивна медицина - Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 268784396

SESSION: NUTRITION AND HEALTH

INVITED LECTURES

1. ACRYLAMIDE IN FOOD

Popović Milka^{1,3}, Torović Lj.^{2,3}, Bjelanović J.^{1,3}, Velicki R.^{1,3}

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Hygiene, Novi Sad, Serbia

²University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Pharmacy, Novi Sad, Serbia

³Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia

Background

Acrylamide (AA, synonyms: 2-propenamide, acrylic amide and ethylene carboxamide) is an important highly reactive industrial chemical that has been widely used since 1950s for the production of polyacrylamides, utilized in different industrial branches. AA, a low molecular weight organic compound, is predominantly used as a building block for water-soluble polymers, which have consumed as additives for flocculants used for drinking water purification and sewage treatment, in paper and cosmetic industry, for soil conditioning, as well as in food packaging. Occasionally, workplace exposure through dermal absorption and/or inhalation can occur.

AA is also present in tobacco smoke, as a non-dietary source of exposure for smokers and non-smokers (through passive smoking). For smokers, tobacco smoking is a more prominent source of acrylamide exposure than food.

In addition, acrylamide is a contaminant and a chemical hazard in the food chain. From the food safety perspective, the turning point was year 2002, when Swedish scientists unexpectedly revealed that many heated foods contained significant levels of AA as a process contaminant, which is the result of the naturally occurring chemical reactions.

Acrylamide formation

Various cooking practices using temperatures greater than 120°C, in a variety of plant-based, carbohydrate-rich foods with low protein content, results in the formation of AA, as a part of the Maillard reaction. Maillard reaction (non-enzymatic browning) is a chemical reaction between free amino acids (asparagine) and reducing sugars (such as glucose/dextrose, fructose) in low moisture conditions that brown foods and enhance their flavor. Additionally, the ingredients, storage, and processing conditions also greatly influence acrylamide formation in food prepared industrially, catered or at home. It is present mainly in baked, grilled or fried foods, so a wide range of foods, including staple food (such as bread, fried potatoes, coffee) as well as other foods like potato crisps, biscuits were found to contain different levels of AA, ranging from few mg/kg to over 1000 mg/kg. There are other possible pathways of AA formation: from carnosine and aminopropionamide as additional precursors, from acrolein and acrylic acid found in food rich in lipids, from purified gluten, etc. It seems that formation of AA does not occur in microwaved or boiled foods.

Identification and characterization of the hazard - acrylamide

Acrylamide is a chemical with well-known toxic properties including neurotoxicity, genotoxicity, carcinogenicity and reproductive toxicity. Evidence from animal studies have shown that acrylamide and its reactive metabolite epoxide glycidamide (GA) are genotoxic and carcinogenic, through its binding to DNA. AA has been classified as a Group 2A carcinogen (probably carcinogenic to humans) by the International Agency for Research on Cancer.

After oral ingestion, acrylamide is rapidly absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract, distributed to all organs and extensively metabolized. Glycidamide is one of the main metabolites, responsible for carcinogenic effects in animals. Biomarkers of AA exposure include their urinary metabolites and adducts with hemoglobin and DNA.

Dietary exposure to acrylamide intensifies distress regarding probable risks for human health. Many international organizations, (UK scientific advisory committees, European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), World Health Organization, to name just some of them) have assessed the risks that acrylamide brings. One of the latest risk assessments studies, done by Scientific Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM) of the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)

determined that despite the fact that so far performed studies in human populations have not confirmed that acrylamide is actually a human carcinogen, the Margin of Exposure (MOEs) based on the up-to-date levels of dietary exposure to acrylamide across studies and age groups indicate a fear regarding its carcinogenic effects. This alarm can be applied to general consumer population. Nevertheless, due to the body weight factor, children are the most exposed and endangered.

In addition to malignancies, the Panel also indicated possible damaging effects of AA on nervous system, male reproduction capabilities, as well as pre- and post-natal development. Nevertheless, based on existing levels of dietary exposure, the aforementioned effects were not considered a concern.

Benchmark Dose and Margin of Exposure

Since any level of exposure to a genotoxic substance could potentially lead to development of malignancy, a tolerable daily intake (TDI) of acrylamide in food could not be established. Instead, EFSA's experts estimated the dose range within which acrylamide is likely to cause a small but perceptible tumor incidence and/or other potentially adverse effects. The lower limit of this range is called the Benchmark Dose Lower Confidence Limit (BMDL₁₀). For tumors, experts determined a BMDL₁₀ of 0.17mg/kg bw/day. Among other effects, neurological changes were seen as the most relevant, with a BMDL₁₀ of 0.43 mg/kg bw/day.

Comparing BMDL₁₀ with human dietary exposure to acrylamide, scientists can indicate a "level of health concern" known as a Margin of Exposure (MOE), an indication about a substance's presence in food without estimating the risk. Use of the MOE can help risk managers to determine activities required to keep exposure as low as possible.

The MOEs for the malignancies-related effects of AA range from 425 for average adult consumers down to 50 for high consuming toddlers. According to EFSA, MOE of 10,000 or higher is considered to be of low concern for public health.

Official controls

Appropriate sampling plans, as well as statistically relevant number of samples are crucial for determination of the AA amount in foods for establishing a baseline for AA level in particular food product and to monitor success of the reducing AA levels strategy.

Sampling of the products should be executed at market level, with a minimum size of 4 samples per product category (a total of 10 different product categories), providing a total annual number between 40 and 230 samples per country, depending on population size.

Methods of analysis

Having in mind the high variability of food matrices and food processing procedures, the choice of the reliable analytical methods is of utmost importance. There is a number of analytical approaches to determining AA in food, including methods based on gas chromatography (GC-MS) or liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-ESI-MS/MS). It is recommended to perform analyses in an accredited laboratories that use validated and approved analytical methods for detection and quantification.

Food that contribute to acrylamide exposure

According to EFSA, foods that mainly contribute to AA exposure in Europe are different depending on age groups.

In adults, different fried potato products account for up to 49% of average exposure, followed by coffee (34%), soft bread (23%), biscuits, crackers and crisp bread, as well as other products based on potato.

In children (toddlers, other children, adolescents), potato fried products account for up to 51% of all dietary exposure. Soft bread, breakfast cereals, biscuits and other products based on cereals or potato can contribute up to 25%. Processed cereal-based baby food represents up to 14% of exposure for toddlers, while cakes and pastry contribute up to 15% in the groups of other children and adolescents; potato crisps and snacks account for 11% of exposure among adolescents.

In infants, baby foods other than processed cereal-based, other products based on potatoes and processed cereal-based baby food (mainly rusks and biscuits) contribute up to 60%, 48% and 30% respectively.

Although some food categories, such as potato crisps and snacks, as well as coffee substitutes contain relatively high levels of acrylamide, their overall contribution to dietary exposure is limited, based on a normal/varied diet.

Reduction of acrylamide levels in foods

Reduction of AA levels in foods has been recommended by many health and food expert authorities, having in mind that measures must not result in increase of other process contaminants nor compromise safety of the product.

The complexity of various factors influencing AA formation in food, including, but not limited to level of precursors of raw materials (e.g. asparagine and reducing sugars), food ingredients, product form (e.g. raising agents, pH, fermentation, dilution), processing elements, such as high temperature, moisture, pre-treatment, added enzymes (asparaginase), texture, flavor, color of the finished product, etc., as well as final preparation performed by end user. Even within a certain product category, different AA reduction strategy and mitigation tools developed by scientists and industries could be utilized. Available scientific literature and data, reviewed by EFSA, indicate how the choice of ingredients, storage method and the temperature at which food is cooked influence the amount of acrylamide in different food types.

However, there is no easy or single solution to reduce AA level in foods. The main food categories for implementing reduction strategies are: potato-based products (French fries, potato crisps, snack and crackers), cereal-based products (bread, crisp bread, breakfast cereals, biscuits and bakery products), roast and ground coffee, instant coffee, coffee substitutes, baby biscuits, infant cereals and baby foods other than cereal based foods.

Most of the strategies and tools are developed and standardized for industrial settings. Home-cooking choices can have a substantial impact on the level of acrylamide. The complete elimination of AA from food doesn't seem feasible using current mitigation approaches. Thus, additional interventions and improvements are needed.

Conclusion

Mitigation approach can be successful in lowering the levels of AA, and it can be done by implementing a good hygiene practices and applying procedures based on hazard analysis and critical control point (HACCP) principles. All food businesses operators should be required to put in place management of AA within their food safety management systems. By doing so, it would be ensured that AA levels are as low as reasonably achievable (ALARA concept) in their products. From April 2018 Commission Regulation (EU) 2017/2158 is in force, establishing best available practice, mitigation measures and benchmark levels for the reduction of the presence of AA in food. AA formation in domestic settings can be reduced by adjusted consumers' behavior at home. Consumers' education regarding reducing exposure to a possible carcinogen while purchasing industrially prepared food, cooking at home is an integral part of the risk management.

Key words: Acrylamide, Food Safety, Hazard, Mitigation, Risk Assessment

Literature

1. Tareke E, Rydberg P, Karlsson P et al. Analysis of acrylamide, a carcinogen formed in heated foodstuffs. *J Agric Food Chem* 2002 Aug 14;50(17):4998-5006.
2. IARC Working Group on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risk to Humans. Some Industrial Chemicals. Lyon (FR): International Agency for Research on Cancer; 1994. (IARC Monographs on the Evaluation of Carcinogenic Risks to Humans, No. 60.) Available from: <https://monographs.iarc.fr/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/mono60-16.pdf>.
3. EFSA CONTAM Panel (EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain), 2015. Scientific Opinion on acrylamide in food. *EFSA Journal* 2015;13(6):4104, 321 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2015.4104 Available from: <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.2903/j.efsa.2015.4104>.
4. Exon JH. A review of the toxicology of acrylamide. *J Toxicol Environ Health B Crit Rev.* 2006 Sep-Oct;9(5):397-412. Review.
5. Yaylayan VA, Stadler RH. Acrylamide formation in food: a mechanistic perspective. *J AOAC Int.* 2005 Jan-Feb;88(1):262-7. Review.
6. EFSA explains risk assessment: Acrylamide in food. Available from: https://www.efsa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/corporate_publications/files/acrylamide150604.pdf.
7. COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2017/2158 establishing mitigation measures and benchmark levels for the reduction of the presence of acrylamide in food). Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2017/2158/oj>.

8. Scientific Advisory Committee on Nutrition (SACN). COMMITTEE ON TOXICITY OF CHEMICALS IN FOOD, CONSUMER PRODUCTS AND THE ENVIRONMENT. Statement on potential risks from acrylamide in the diet of infants and young children. COT Statement 2016/07, October 2016. Available from: https://cot.food.gov.uk/sites/default/files/finalstatementonarsenic_0.pdf.
9. Seal CJ, de Mul A, Eisenbrand G, Haverkort AJ, Franke K, Lalljie SP, et al. Risk-benefit considerations of mitigation measures on acrylamide content of foods--a case study on potatoes, cereals and coffee. *Br J Nutr.* 2008 Apr;99 Suppl 2:S1-S46. doi: 10.1017/S0007114508965314.
10. FoodDrinkEurope. Acrylamide toolbox 2017. Available from: http://www.uvhvvr.gov.si/fileadmin/uvhvvr.gov.si/pageuploads/DELOVNA_PODROCJA/Zivila/onesn_azevala/Food_Drink_Europe_Acrylamide_Toolbox_2017__4-New.pdf.